

Time Series Lossy Compression Using Wavelet, Fourier, and Cosine Transforms: Benchmarking Optimisation Parameters, Compression Ratios, and Decompression Error

Simon Kraus

simon.kraus@campus.tu-berlin.de
Berlin, Germany

Abstract

Nowadays, time series data is collected and analyzed in enormous quantities. Managing such large volumes quickly leads to high storage and transmission costs, making lossy compression often the only viable solution. However, choosing the optimal compression method is particularly challenging: not only must a method be selected from a wide range of options, but each method also has numerous parameter settings that can greatly affect performance and accuracy. To address this, we compare three transformation-based lossy compression methods—Discrete Wavelet Transform, Discrete Cosine Transform, and Discrete Fourier Transform—across eight time series datasets.

Keywords

Time Series Analysis, Lossy Compression, Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT)

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of time series data in multiple domains has made efficient storage and transmission a critical challenge. For example, wind turbines continuously record rotor speed, blade pitch, and power output; air quality sensors track pollutants such as benzene and particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10) along with meteorological variables; and industrial monitoring systems generate streams of operational data. The large volume of these high-frequency measurements creates high storage and transmission costs, making lossy compression a practical necessity. While compression reduces data size, it irreversibly alters the signal, which may affect analyses such as fault detection in turbines or pollution forecasting in environmental monitoring.

A wide variety of transformation-based lossy compression methods exist, each with multiple parameter settings that influence performance. For instance, the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) requires choosing a wavelet function, decomposition level, and quantization precision. Similarly, Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) rely on quantization choices to balance compression efficiency and reconstruction accuracy. Selecting optimal parameters is critical: poor choices could distort rotor speed patterns in turbines, obscure pollutant trends in air quality data, or misrepresent other environmental signals, leading to inaccurate predictions or missed events.

This study focuses on identifying optimal parameter configurations for DWT-, DCT-, and DFT-based compression and comparing

their performance in terms of the trade-off between compression ratio (CR) and decompression error. By systematically evaluating these three methods across eight distinct time series datasets, we aim to provide guidance on selecting both the most suitable compression method and its parameter settings for efficient and accurate time series lossy compression in real-world applications. Building on this goal, we formulate two primary research questions (RQ) to guide our investigation.

- **RQ1:** What parameter configurations yield the best performance across DWT-, DCT-, and DFT-based compression methods?
 - **RQ1.1:** What is the optimal decomposition level in achieving high CR and low decompression error in DWT-based compression?
 - **RQ1.2:** Which wavelet function provides the optimal performance for DWT-based compression?
 - **RQ1.3:** What is the optimal quantisation precision for DWT-, DCT-, and DFT-based compression?
- **RQ2:** Which of the DWT-, DCT-, and DFT-based compression methods provides the optimal trade-off compression ratio and decompression error?

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1.1 (Time Series): A *time series* T is an ordered list of N data points, indexed in time order. Each data point is a tuple consisting of a timestamp t_i and a corresponding value v_i , where $v_i \in \mathbb{R}$. It is formulated as: $T = \{(t_0, v_0), (t_1, v_1), \dots, (t_{N-1}, v_{N-1})\}$

Time Series Compression: Compressing a time series is the process of converting a time series to another representation that is smaller in size. Time series decompression, on the other hand, is the reverse process of compression, where the aim is to reconstruct the original time series from its compressed representation. The decompression is *lossless* when the decompression algorithm returns a time series identical to the original time series, whereas the decompression is *lossy* when the decompressed time series is not identical to the original time series [4]. In this study, we focus on lossy compression using domain transforms.

Transformation-based Lossy Compression: Transformation-based compression is a lossy compression method that involves converting the input time series from its original time domain into an alternative domain e.g., the frequency domain. Generally, in this alternative domain, the time series is represented in a more efficient way using coefficients, with most of the time series important information, such as the general shape and key patterns, concentrated in a small subset of coefficients. This allows the discarding

of less significant coefficients in the alternative domain, achieving compression while preserving essential information. Generally, coefficients with higher absolute values, in this context called magnitudes, contain more important information. Therefore, to achieve compression, coefficients are ordered after their absolute value and then a specific percentage of the smallest coefficients is set to zero. Decompression is achieved by applying the inverse domain transform on the remaining coefficients, transforming the time series back into time domain. The described procedure of the transformation-based lossy compression and decompression can be found in Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2, respectively. The degree to which the time series is reduced in size depends on the number of coefficients that are set to zero in the alternative domain. To quantify this measure, we introduce what we term dropout percentage.

Definition 2.1.1 (Dropout Percentage): We define the dropout percentage as the percentage of coefficients that are set to zero after transforming a time series from time domain into an alternative domain. The higher the dropout percentage, the more coefficients are set to zero, the greater the reduction in data size. In the scope of this study we use we use the dropout percentages: 0, 0.5, 0.75, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95, 0.97 and 0.99.

Algorithm 1 Transformation-Based Compression Algorithm

Input: Time series $T_v = [v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{N-1}]$, dropout percentage d
Output: Compressed coefficients $C_{\text{compressed}}$

```

 $C_{\text{original}} \leftarrow \text{forward\_transform}(T_v)$ 
 $r \leftarrow \lfloor d \times N \rfloor$ 
 $I_{\text{sorted}} \leftarrow \text{argsort}(|C_{\text{original}}|)$ 
 $I_{\text{drop}} \leftarrow I_{\text{sorted}}[0 : r]$ 
for all  $i \in I_{\text{drop}}$  do
   $C_{\text{original}}[i] \leftarrow 0$ 
end for
 $C_{\text{compressed}} \leftarrow C_{\text{original}}$ 
return  $C_{\text{compressed}}$ 

```

Algorithm 2 Transformation-Based Decompression Algorithm

Input: Compressed Coefficients: $C_{\text{compressed}} = [c'_0, c'_1, \dots, c'_{N-1}]$
Output: Reconstructed Time Series: $\hat{T}_v = [\hat{v}_0, \hat{v}_1, \dots, \hat{v}_{N-1}]$

```

 $\hat{T}_v \leftarrow \text{inverse\_transform}(C_{\text{compressed}})$ 
return  $\hat{T}_v$ 

```

We evaluate three domain transforms that are repeatedly cited in scientific literature and some of which play a significant role in several state of the art compression algorithms [1] [11] [9]. These three domain transforms—DFT, DCT, and DWT—are described below.

DFT: The DFT transforms a time series from time-domain into frequency domain, by decomposing it into a sum of sine and cosine components. For an univariate time series $T = [(t_0, v_0), \dots, (t_{N-1}, v_{N-1})]$ the DFT and its inverse are defined as follows.

DFT:

$$c_k = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_n \cdot e^{-i2\pi \frac{k}{N} n}$$

Inverse DFT:

$$v_n = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} c_k \cdot e^{i2\pi \frac{k}{N} n}$$

Where:

- (1) c_k is the k -th DFT coefficient, $k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1\}$
- (2) v_n is the n -th value of the time series, $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1\}$
- (3) $e^{\frac{2\pi i}{N}}$ is a primitive N -th root of unity

The resulting coefficients c_k are complex values, which contain information about both the magnitude and the phase of the frequency component. Generally, the larger the magnitude of a frequency component, the more important information about the original signal it contains. In practical applications, typically the Fast Fourier Transform algorithm is used to improve computational efficiency [5].

DCT: DCT is similar to DFT in that it transforms a time series from time domain into frequency domain. But, unlike DFT, the DCT only uses cosine functions to represent the signal. Thus, it transforms a sequence of real numbers into another sequence of real numbers. For an univariate time series $T = [(t_0, v_0), \dots, (t_{N-1}, v_{N-1})]$ the DCT and its inverse are defined as follows.

DCT:

$$c_k = w(k) \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} v_n \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2N} k(2n+1)\right)$$

Inverse DCT:

$$v_n = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} w(k) c_k \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2N} k(2n+1)\right)$$

where:

- (1) c_k is the k -th DCT coefficient, $k \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1\}$
- (2) v_n is the n -th value of the time series, $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1\}$
- (3) $w(k) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N}} & \text{for } n = 0 \\ \sqrt{\frac{2}{N}} & \text{for } n \neq 0 \end{cases}$

DCT plays a major role in the widely established JPEG image compression standard [11].

(DWT) Whereas in DFT the time series is represented in terms of sine and cosine components, in the DWT wavelets are used to represent the time series. Wavelets are functions that, like a tiny wave, begin at zero and end at zero after some oscillation. A mother wavelet $\Psi(t)$ serves as a fundamental function form which a set of wavelets is derived, each a shifted and scaled version of the mother wavelet. Shifting can be interpreted as moving the wavelet along the time axis, allowing it to capture features of the time series at different time locations. Scaling is adjusting the width of the wavelet, allowing it to capture different frequency components of the time series. This shifting and scaling of the mother wavelet allows an analysis of both the time and the frequency domain, unlike the DFT or DCT, which only provide frequency information. The forward DWT and inverse DWT are defined as:

DWT:

$$c_{j,k} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)\Psi_{j,k}(t) dt$$

Inverse DWT:

$$x(t) = \sum_{j,k} c_{j,k}\Psi_{j,k}(t)$$

Where:

- (1) $x(t)$ is the function to be transformed
- (2) $\Psi_{j,k}$ is the mother wavelet Ψ shifted with k and scaled with j . It is defined as:

$$\Psi_{j,k}(t) = 2^{-\frac{j}{2}}\Psi(2^{-j}t - k)$$

- (3) $c_{j,k}$ is the wavelet coefficient

DWT Computation: DWT is typically computed by deriving high-pass F_{high} and low-pass filters F_{low} from a mother wavelet and its corresponding scaling function. The high-pass filter emphasizes high-frequency components of the time series, capturing abrupt changes and fine details, while the low-pass filter emphasizes low-frequency components, capturing the general patterns and overall trend. Applying these filters simultaneously to the input time series results in approximation coefficients A^j and detail coefficients D^j , produced by the low-pass filter and high-pass filter respectively. The input time series gets decomposed over several decomposition levels j , where in each step the filters are applied only on the approximation coefficients of the current level A^j , splitting it into another pair of approximation coefficients A^{j+1} and detail coefficients D^{j+1} . This process is repeated iteratively, with each level providing a finer level of detail. Further, in each step, the approximation and detail coefficients are down-sampled by two, as half the coefficients contain redundant information. The procedure is shown in 1, where the input time series T gets decomposed over three decomposition levels.

Figure 1: DWT three level decomposition using high-pass and low-pass filters

The main task in transformation-based compression using DWT is finding an optimal combination of mother wavelet and decomposition level that allows a decomposition of the time series, where most of the important information is stored in an optimally small subset of coefficients. Therefore, in this study, we conduct experimental evaluation, to find the optimal parameters for DWT compression. Furthermore, we improve the effectiveness of the transformation-based compression methods through quantization.

Quantization Quantization is a form of lossy compression where a large set of values is mapped to a smaller set of values, generally by approximating or rounding the values. This reduces variability in the data and makes patterns more consistent. As a result, applying then a lossless compression algorithm leads to more efficient compression, since these algorithms generally perform better on data with more repetitive patterns and fewer unique sequences. In our case, after applying a domain transform on the time series, many coefficients usually differ only in the last few decimal places, so rounding down the coefficients to a lower number of decimal places can lead to higher compression with relatively low information loss.

Definition 2.1.2 (Quantization Precision): We term quantization precision the number of decimal places after which the coefficient values are cut off when applying quantization. For example, quantizing $c_k = 3.14569999$ with a quantization precision of three results in $\hat{c}_k = 3.145$.

3 Experimental Design

3.1 Datasets

For our experiment, we use datasets with different characteristics from various fields to cover a large range of distinct time series, so that - ideally - our results can be generalized well across different types of data. Additionally, we select publicly available datasets to make sure the results can be easily reproduced. An overview of the datasets is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Datasets Overview

Dataset	No. Time Series	Length	No. Dimensions	Missing
AppliancesEnergy	138	144	24	No
PowerUsage	1440	1440	5	Yes
BenzeneConcentration	8878	240	8	Yes
ParticulateMatter2.5	17532	24	9	Yes
ParticulateMatter10	17532	24	9	Yes
Flood	673	266	1	No
IEEPPG	3096	1000	5	No
Covid	201	84	1	No

AppliancesEnergy: This dataset contains 138 time series, each with 24 dimensions. The dimensions represent humidity and temperature measurements of 9 different rooms in a house and weather and climate data from nearby airport, including measurements of temperature, pressure, humidity, wind speed, visibility, and dew point. The data is averaged every 10 minutes with each time series spanning over 1 day. The time series contain no missing values and the data originates from the Appliances Energy Prediction dataset from the UCI repository [3] [10].

PowerUsage: This dataset consists of 1440, 5-dimensional time series, including measurements for voltage, current, and 3 sub-metering energy usages. Each time series spans over 24 hours and is minutely sampled. The time series contain missing values and the data originates from the UCI machine learning repository [7].

BenzeneConcentration: This dataset consists of 8878 time series. Each time series contains 8 dimensions, with outputs from 5 metal oxide chemical sensors in an Air Quality Chemical Multisensor Device, together with data on relative humidity, absolute humidity, and temperature. The data is hourly averaged and each time series spans over 10 days. The target variable is the benzene concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of the current hour, using the hourly measurements from the last 10 days. The time series contains missing values and was sourced from the UCI machine learning repository [16] [17].

ParticulateMatter2.5: This dataset includes 17532, 9-dimensional time series with hourly measurements of sulfur dioxide (SO_2), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), carbon monoxide (CO), and ozone (O_3), along with temperature, pressure, dew point, rainfall, and wind speed. Each time series is hourly sampled and spans over 24 hours. The time series contain missing values [16] [20].

ParticulateMatter10: This dataset includes 17532, 9-dimensional time series with hourly measurements of sulfur dioxide (SO_2), nitrogen dioxide (NO_2), carbon monoxide (CO), and ozone (O_3), along with temperature, pressure, dew point, rainfall, and wind speed. Each time series is hourly sampled and spans over 24 hours. The time series contain missing values [16].

Flood: This dataset consists of 673, 1-dimensional time series representing hourly (mm/h) rainfall spanning 226 hours. The time series contain no missing values and the data was synthetically generated [16].

IEEEPPG: This dataset contains 3096 time series, each with 5 dimensions. The dimensions consist of measurements of two-channel PPG signals, three-axis acceleration signals, and one-channel ECG signals, which were simultaneously recorded from test subjects aged 18 to 35. All signals were sampled at 125 Hz. The time series contain no missing values and the data originates from the IEEE Signal Processing Cup 2015: Heart Rate Monitoring During Physical Exercise Using Wrist-Type Photoplethysmographic (PPG) Signals [16] [21].

Covid: The aim of the dataset is to predict the death rate of Covid-19 as of April 1, 2020, for each country using the daily confirmed cases for the last 3 months. It contains 201 time series, where each time series is the daily confirmed Covid-19 cases for a country from January to March 2020. The time series have no missing values and the data originates from WHO's official COVID-19 database [16] [18].

3.2 Compression Implementation

Figure 2 provides an overview of the steps involved in the implementation of compression and decompression, both of which we explain in further detail below.

Figure 2: Compression and Decompression Methodology

Compression: To compress a dataset, we drop the timestamp of each single time series and store the dataset in as a multidimensional array. In datasets with missing values, the missing data points are linearly interpolated. Then we apply z-score normalization (standardization) on each single time series to make it more suitable for later analysis. In datasets where the individual time series have lengths less than 1000, we concatenate the time series for each dimension and then split them into chunks that are close to size 1000. The exact size of a chunk depends on the size of the individual time series per dataset. If the last chunk in each dimension has a size less than 500, it is concatenated with the chunk before, otherwise it is treated as a separate chunk. Afterward, we apply the forward transform on these time series chunks, transforming the time series values to transformation coefficients. Next, we set the coefficients with lowest absolute values to zero, with the number of coefficients

we discard defined by the dropout percentage. Following, we round down the remaining coefficient a certain number of decimal places specified by the quantization precision. After that we apply gzip compression on the coefficients, using the highest possible gzip compression level. The file size of the resulting gzip file is the size of the compressed dataset.

Decompression For decompression, we first decompress the gzip file, restore the time series chunks and then apply the inverse transform on these chunks. Finally, we split the resulting chunks of concatenated time series back into individual time series.

Selecting Wavelets: There are many individual wavelets from lots of different families to choose from. However, for considerable amount of wavelets, there has been not much comprehensive research conducted in terms of their impact on time series compression. Therefore, we only compare wavelets that already demonstrated notable potential in compression, namely Haar, Debauchies and Biorthogonal wavelets. Each of them has been studied in prior scientific research and highlights distinct properties. Haar wavelets can lead to very high compression ratios and indicate good compression on time series with sharp transitions and abrupt changes. Debauchies seem to generalize well over many different types of time series and deliver a good compromise between CR and decompression error. Biorthogonal wavelets have shown comparable performance than Debauchies, although a little bit less robust [9] [15]. Yet, Biorthogonal wavelets demonstrate good performance in other compression fields such as image compression [14] [2] and compressive sensing [19], a method of simultaneously sensing and compressing a signal. Specifically we select the Biorthogonal 3.5 wavelet (*bior3.5*), Debauchies 4 (*db4*) and Haar (*haar*) wavelet for evaluation.

Libraries: We use SciPy’s Fast Fourier Transform implementation for DFT compression and SciPy’s Discrete Cosine Transform implementation for DCT compression. For DWT compression we use the PyWavelet library. Further, in DWT we apply the signal extension mode *periodization*.

4 Results Analysis

4.1 RQ1: Identifying Optimal Compression Parameters

In contrast to DCT and DFT, where the only remaining parameter is the dropout percentage, DWT compression requires selection of two additional parameters, namely the specific wavelet and the decomposition level. First, we identify the optimal decomposition level for each wavelet and then we determine which wavelet yields the best results over all datasets.

Identifying Optimal Decomposition Levels (RQ1.1): To find the optimal decomposition level for each selected wavelet, we compare the dropout percentage against decompression error over each possible decomposition level. Figure 3 shows the results for the *db4* wavelet. The fairly similar results for *haar* and *bior3.5* can be found in the Appendix (Figure 7 and Figure 8). For the *db4* wavelet in Figure 3 the results show that the maximum decomposition level leads for six out of eight datasets across every dropout percentage to the best decompression error. Only in two datasets, namely Covid and Flood, the results are ambiguous. Here the maximum decomposition level leads for the smaller dropout percentages still

to the best error, but for the higher dropout values the minimal decomposition level yields now the lowest decompression error. The results for *haar* and *bior3.5* wavelets are fairly similar to those from *db4*, except that for the *bior3.5* wavelet in ParticulateMatter 10 for dropout percentage 0.97 and 0.99 the minimal decomposition level yields the best error instead of the maximal decomposition level. To conclude, over all dropout percentages and all datasets the best decompression error originates for the most part from the maximum decomposition level.

Figure 3: Dropout percentage vs. decompression error over all decomposition level for *db4* wavelet. L denotes the decomposition levels.

Identifying Optimal Wavelets (RQ2): After identifying the optimal decomposition level, we can now evaluate which wavelets perform best over all datasets. For that we compare the dropout percentage against the decompression error for each wavelet, as displayed in Figure 4. The results are very straightforward: The *db4* wavelet yields the best decompression error over each dropout percentage for AppliancesEnergy, BenzeneConcentration, IEEPPG, ParticulateMatter2.5 and ParticulateMatter10, whereas the *haar* wavelet consistently achieves best decompression error on Covid, Flood and PowerUsage.

Consequently, the analysis indicates that, depending on the dataset, the *haar* and *db4* wavelets at the highest decomposition level are the optimal parameters for DWT compression. Thus, we select the highest decomposition level and the *haar* wavelet for Covid, Flood and PowerUsage and *db4* for AppliancesEnergy, BenzeneConcentration, IEEPPG, ParticulateMatter2.5.

Figure 4: Dropout percentage vs. decompression error for each wavelet db4, haar and bior3.5 wavelet

Identifying optimal Quantization Precisions (RQ1.3): To find the optimal quantization precision, we compare for each dropout percentage the CR against the decompression error over six quantization precisions (precision 0 to precision 5). The results for DFT are visualized in Figure 5. The plots for DWT and DCT can be found in the Appendix (Figure 9 and Figure 10). Each of the eight datapoints per quantization precision corresponds to one dropout values (0, 0.5, 0.75, 0.85, 0.9, 0.95, 0.97, 0.99). For dropout value zero we simply apply no compression and return a CR of one. Otherwise the CR could be smaller than one, since the coefficients after the transformation, without discarding a certain percentage, have typically higher variability and entropy than the raw time series values itself. The results for DCT are very clear. For each dropout value, a lower quantization precision yields a higher CR, while not significantly affecting the decompression error. Thus, for DCT we select quantization precision of zero. On the other hand, in DFT and DWT for quantization precision one to five, the results are similar to DCT: The lower the quantization precision, the higher the CR while not substantially increasing the decompression error. But for quantization precision zero, the small dropout percentages already start at a relatively high decompression error in some datasets, e.g in AppliancesEnergy for dropout percentage 0.5 the decompression error starts already at 0.22. Thus, if we choose quantization precision of zero, we couldn't cover smaller decompression errors and the first few dropout percentages would be rather uninteresting. However, for the last few dropout percentages, the quantization

precision of zero has a fairly similar error than the other precisions, just better CRs. These results indicate that for DWT and DFT, quantization precision of one is most effective across dropout percentages ranging from 0 to 0.95, while quantization precision of zero is preferable at higher dropout percentages of 0.97 and 0.99. For DCT, the findings consistently show that a quantization precision of zero yields better compression ratios at comparable decompression errors than other precision levels. Overall, these results suggest that precision one is optimal for most dropout values in DWT and DFT, with precision zero reserved for extreme dropout scenarios, whereas DCT benefits from precision zero across all dropout values.

Figure 5: CR vs. decompression error for quantization precision 0 to 4 for DFT.

4.2 Evaluating the CR–Decompression Error Trade-off (RQ2)

To address RQ2 and determine which compression method has the least impact on the time series, we compare the CR against the decompression error for each lossy compression method over all eight datasets. The results are visualized in Figure 6.

In each graph of CR versus decompression error, we see a similar pattern: as the CR increases, the error rises quickly at first, then slows down and flattens at higher CR values. This indicates that beyond a certain point, increasing compression has a smaller effect on error. Further, it can be observed that the range of CR and decompression error depends strongly on the specific dataset. For example, for a CR of 25, DWT produces a decompression error of

0.19 in BenzeneConcentration, but a decompression error of 0.81 in Covid. Further, for highest dropout percentage, BenzeneConcentration gets compressed up to a CR of 250, whereas in Covid only a CR of around 30 is reached. The low CR in Covid is likely due to the fact that the raw Covid dataset contains a large number of zeros (more than 50%). This leads to already very effective lossless compression, resulting in a low CR, as we apply gzip to both the raw and compressed datasets before calculating the CR.

Analyzing the results to determine the overall best compression method (RQ2), it is clear that none of the three compression approaches consistently outperforms the others. Rather it depends on the dataset individually. In half the datasets DWT generally produces the lowest decompression error, whereas in the other half the results are mostly mixed. Specifically, DWT leads to the best results in Flood and PowerUsage, yielding the lowest decompression error for each CR. Further, in Covid and AppliancesEnergy, DWT also delivers the best outcome for the most part, but for very high CRs - derived from a dropout ratio of 0.99 - DFT compression performs better. In ParticulateMatter2.5 and ParticulateMatter10, DWT compression leads for the lower CRs to the lowest decompression error, but for CRs larger than 32, DFT compression yields the better results. In BenzeneConcentration, DFT compression demonstrates the best performance overall, yielding the lowest decompression error across the majority of compression ratios. Finally, in the IEEPPG dataset DWT and DFT yield similar results, both outperforming DCT for every CR. In conclusion, while results vary across datasets, DWT and DFT clearly outperform DCT. Specifically, in AppliancesEnergy, Flood, PowerUsage, and Covid, DCT consistently produces a worse decompression error than the other two methods for for each CR. In the remaining datasets, DCT rarely outperforms either of the other methods and never surpasses both simultaneously at any CR. Moreover, DWT shows slight overall better results than DFT.

5 Related Work

The field of transformation-based lossy compression on time series analysis is a developing area of study and only a handful of studies primarily focus on this topic. Most studies explored the effect of transformation-based compression on the subsequent time series analysis covering forecasting, change detection and time series classification. For example, [12] examined the influence of three transformation-based lossy compression methods, especially DCT, DWT and the Fast Walsh-Hadamard Transform [6], on four classifications algorithms on agricultural data. Overall, they found that, although lossy compression achieves high CR, its impact varies on classification accuracy among the evaluated datasets and algorithms. [8] conducts an extensive evaluation of lossy compression on change detection, using DWT, Chebyshev Approximation and three other lossy compression methods on five different change detection techniques. One of its conclusions is that the results highly depend on the dataset, e.g the same change detection algorithm is the best performing algorithm in one decompressed dataset and the worst in another. [13] compares wavelet, contourlet, and ripplelet transform compression for medical images, finding that transform-domain methods are promising. Likewise, [4] surveys time-series

Figure 6: CR vs decompression error for DWT, DCT and DFT compression.

compression approaches, illustrating the large variety of available techniques.

Generally, these preliminary studies indicate that transformation-based lossy compression has potential in delivering high CR while maintaining a low decompression error and, consequently, has the chance to not affect the time series analysis substantially. However, in many cases, the results varied strongly depending on the compression method and parameter setting, which underlines the fact that more research is necessary. Thus, to the best of our knowledge, no prior research has been conducted that systemically explores the optimal parameter configurations and CR-decompression error tradeoff for DCT, DFT and DWT on time series data ; therefore, we decided to address this gap.

References

- [1] Mohd Ali Moustafa Yousif Alsayyih, Dzulkifli Mohamad, Tanzila Saba, Amjad Rehman, and Jarallah S Al-Ghamdi. 2017. A Novel Fused Image Compression Technique Using DFT, DWT, and DCT. *J. Inf. Hiding Multim. Signal Process.* 8, 2 (2017), 261–271.
- [2] J. Azpiroz, S. Charleston, and J.-F. Lerallut. 1999. Selection of biorthogonal filters for image compression/fusion of MR images using wavelet packets. In *Proceedings of the First Joint BMES/EMBS Conference. 1999 IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology 21st Annual Conference and the 1999 Annual Fall Meeting of the Biomedical Engineering Society (Cat. N, Vol. 2. 1157 vol.2-)*. doi:10.1109/IEMBS.1999.804323
- [3] Luis Candanedo. 2017. Appliances Energy Prediction. UCI Machine Learning Repository. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C5VC8G>.
- [4] Giacomo Chiarot and Claudio Silvestri. 2023. Time Series Compression Survey. *Comput. Surveys* 55, 10 (2023), Article 198, 32 pages. doi:10.1145/3560814
- [5] James W. Cooley and John W. Tukey. 1965. An Algorithm for the Machine Calculation of Complex Fourier Series. *Math. Comp.* 19 (1965), 297–301. doi:10.

- 1090/S0025-5718-1965-0178586-1
- [6] Monir T Hamood and Said Boussakta. 2011. Fast walsh–hadamard–fourier transform algorithm. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* 59, 11 (2011), 5627–5631.
 - [7] Georges Hebrail and Alice Berard. 2006. Individual Household Electric Power Consumption. UCI Machine Learning Repository. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24432/C58K54>.
 - [8] Gregor Hollmig, Matthias Horne, Simon Leimkühler, Frederik Schöll, Carsten Strunk, Adrian Englhardt, Pavel Efros, Erik Buchmann, and Klemens Böhm. 2017. An evaluation of combinations of lossy compression and change-detection approaches for time-series data. *Information Systems* 65 (2017), 65–77. doi:10.1016/j.is.2016.11.001
 - [9] Samsul Ariffin Abdul Karim, Mohd Hafizi Kamarudin, Bakri Abdul Karim, Mohammad Khatim Hasan, and Jumat Sulaiman. 2011. Wavelet Transform and Fast Fourier Transform for signal compression: A comparative study. In *2011 International Conference on Electronic Devices, Systems and Applications (ICEDSA)*. 280–285. doi:10.1109/ICEDSA.2011.5959031
 - [10] Dominique Deramaix Luis M. Candanedo, Veronique Feldheim. 2017. Data driven prediction models of energy use of appliances in a low-energy house. *Energy and Buildings* 140 (2017), 81–97. doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.01.083
 - [11] Michael Marcellin, Michael Gormish, Ali Bilgin, and Martin Boliek. 2000. Overview of JPEG-2000. *Data Compression Conference Proceedings* (05 2000).
 - [12] Aekyung Moon, Jaeyoung Kim, Jialing Zhang, and Seung Woo Son. 2018. Evaluating fidelity of lossy compression on spatiotemporal data from an IoT enabled smart farm. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 154 (11 2018), 304–313. doi:10.1016/j.compag.2018.08.045
 - [13] Eben Sophia Paul and J. Anitha. 2019. Chapter 5 - Analysis of Transform-Based Compression Techniques for MRI and CT Images. In *Intelligent Data Analysis for Biomedical Applications*, D. Jude Hemanth, Deepak Gupta, and Valentina Emilia Balas (Eds.). Academic Press, 103–120. doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-815553-0.00005-7
 - [14] Singh Priyanka, Priti Singh, and Rakesh Sharma. 2011. JPEG Image Compression based on Biorthogonal, Coiflets and Daubechies Wavelet Families. *International Journal of Computer Applications* 13 (01 2011). doi:10.5120/1748-2382
 - [15] K Ranjeet, A Kumar, and Rajesh K Pandey. 2011. ECG signal compression using different techniques. In *International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Control*. Springer, 231–241.
 - [16] TSE Regression Project. 2024. Time Series Extrinsic Regression. <http://tseregression.org/> Accessed: 2024-10-27.
 - [17] S. De Vito, E. Massera, M. Piga, L. Martinotto, and G. Di Francia. 2008. On field calibration of an electronic nose for benzene estimation in an urban pollution monitoring scenario. 750-757 pages. doi:10.1016/j.snb.2007.09.060
 - [18] World Health Organization. 2024. WHO Coronavirus (COVID-19) Dashboard. <https://covid19.who.int> Accessed: 2024-10-27.
 - [19] Shunliao Yang, Zhengbing Zhang, Hong Du, Zhenghua Xia, and Hongying Qin. 2010. The Compressive Sensing Based on Biorthogonal Wavelet Basis. In *2010 International Symposium on Intelligence Information Processing and Trusted Computing*. 479–482. doi:10.1109/IPTC.2010.146
 - [20] S. Zhang, B. Guo, A. Dong, J. He, Z. Xu, and S.X. Chen. 2017. Cautionary Tales on Air-Quality Improvement in Beijing. 20170457 pages. doi:10.1098/rspa.2017.0457
 - [21] Z. Zhang, Z. Pi, and B. Liu. 2015. TROIKA: A general framework for heart rate monitoring using wrist-type photoplethysmographic signals during intensive physical exercise. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 62, 2 (February 2015), 522–531. doi:10.1109/TBME.2014.2359372

6 Appendices

Figure 7: Dropout percentage vs. decompression error over all decomposition levels for *haar* wavelet. L denotes the decomposition level.

Figure 8: Dropout percentage vs. decompression error over all decomposition levels for *bior3.5* wavelet. L denotes the decomposition level.

Figure 10: CR vs. decomposition error for quantization precision 0 to 4 for DCT. Note, in Covid dropout percentage 0.5 has a CR < 1 because the Covid dataset already contains many zeros.

Figure 9: CR vs. decomposition error for quantization precision 0 to 4 for DWT.